

A STUDY OF EMPOWERMENT OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS IN HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF BAREILLY DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out to study and compare the level of empowerment among higher secondary girls of Bareilly district in reference to their locality, stream, religion and age. The sample of 145 higher secondary girls was randomly selected from government and private higher secondary schools of Bareilly district. "Adolescent Girls empowerment scale 'AGES' developed and standardized by Dr. Devendra Singh Sisodia and Dr Alpana Singh was used to collect the data. The findings revealed that there was no significant difference among higher secondary girls level of adolescent girls empowerment in reference of their locality, age and religion. There is a significant difference among higher secondary girls level of adolescent girls empowerment in reference of their stream.

Keywords: Adolescent Girls, Empowerment, Locality And Stream.

I. INTRODUCTION

India has about 230 million adolescent in the age group 10-19 year with female comprising about 47% of total Adolescent Population, The term adolescence has been defined by WHO as a period of life where a series of varied, rapid and extensive change occurs. For both boys and girls, adolescence is a critical growth stage. Girls experience various changes throughout this time period. In terms of health and developmental results during early childhood, boys and girls perform almost equally well, but during puberty, girls confront numerous difficulties.

In comparison to boys, girls experience biological and social changes during adolescence more quickly. Girls in this time period go through puberty earlier than boys, which means they have to deal with social and developmental issues associated to sexual maturation earlier in life. The primary issue for girls is child marriage in their early years. One-third of the world's population marries before age 18, and one-third of women in developing nations marry before age 20.

Adolescence

Adolescence is characterised by the fast physical and psychological changes that occur in a person, as well as the mounting demands and influences of friends, school, and society at large. The significance of the behaviours that are formed during this time on adult health is widely established. Many health-harming behaviours (like drinking alcohol and smoking) as well as health-improving behaviours (like exercising) are picked up throughout adolescence and frequently continue into adulthood. According to the World Health Organization, adolescent-onset behaviours including smoking, using illegal drugs, and careless driving account for 70% of adult premature deaths. Therefore, it is imperative to assist teenagers in building healthy lifestyles and avoiding the development of health risk behaviours, and this assistance should begin before these habits become established.

Adolescent girls are very important part of our society as they are our potential mothers and future homemakers. During adolescent period of human growth due to growth spurt, the risk of iron deficiency and Anaemia appears to be more for boys and girls and in girls it remains as such during reproduction life several studies on the prevalence of anaemia among adolescent girls have been carried out in the northern or southern parts of India (Gawarikar and Tripathi, 2002)

Empowerment

Women have unequal status and position in practically all societies; as a result, it is necessary to empower them by offering them equal possibilities. The concept of empowerment refers to a multifaceted societal process that gives individuals authority over their own life. It can also be described as a process that develops people's

power so they can utilise it to make decisions on topics they believe are crucial for their own lives, communities, and society.

Girls' empowerment is a process of learning by which women identify by their own potential and accordingly they change to perform better in the society. The Oxford American Dictionary defines "empowerment" as "to make (someone) stronger and more confident, esp. in controlling their life and claiming their rights." It means to give women power and help them face the challenges of being a woman in society. Empowering is not given by anyone but it is a process of gaining inside and to use it for the adjustment of life.

Girls' empowerment is essential for the overall growth of society. The meaning of the word "empowerment" varies depending on the situation. Self-determination, freedom, self-power, self-control, self-reliance, and advocating for one's rights are all examples of what is meant by empowerment. In addition to making up half of human civilization, women are the foundation of the family. For many families, she is an emotionally resolute force. She participates in all religious rituals and social events on an equal basis with men.

Women should have equal rights and opportunities to participate in education, economics and politics. Only 29% of women serve in the nation workforce in the village many girls suffer from malnutrition. In many situations a girl child is not allowed to complete her education. Our government knows that India can move from developing country to development country if men and women got equal rights, for this our central and state government is running many programs for the empowerment of girls as- Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme, Women Helpline Scheme, Ujjawala (2007), National Mission for Empowerment of Women, Integrated Child Development Service (ICDS) (1975), Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls (RGSEAG) (2010), The Rajiv Gandhi National Creche Scheme for Children of Working Mothers, Integrated Child Protection Scheme (ICPS) (2009-2010).

Education and Girls Empowerment

Education is a powerful tool of social transformation. Hence, education for girls has to be paid special attention. Greater access for girls to education must be ensured in the educational system, Gender sensitivity must be developed. A watch has to be kept on dropout rate of girls and corrective measures should be taken to check the dropout rates. In the field of education there are many schemes were launched by government for empowering girls of India. In the field of education, 2180 residential Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya schools have been sanctioned and are providing elementary education to 1,82,000 out of school girls.

Many studies have conducted related to woman empowerment. The summary of it as follows-

According to Alpana Singh (2000) adjustment level of tribal women was more than adjustment of rural women. Further she found that personality depends on their place and stay. Rural women have been personality than tribal women.

Panda D. (2017) investigated on "Women Empowerment in India: Rational and Present State." He found that women empowerment is not necessary fact for our country but it is a must sustainable development of a nation. It is required to change the mindset of people in India for women. The man should feel that the world is moving towards equality and equity. Hence women empowerment will bring prosperity for the coming generation.

Shettar, R.M. (2015) in her article entitled "A study on Issue and Challenges of women Empowerment in India" opined that empowerment of women could only be achieved if their economic and social status is improved. This could be possible only by adopting definite social and economic policies with a view of total development of women and to make them realize that they have the potential to be strong human beings. Globalization, liberalization and other socio-economic forces have given some respite to a large proportion of the population. However, there are still quite a few areas where women empowerment in India is largely lacking.

Khatri, R. (2016) conducted a study entitled "The Role of Education towards Women Empowerment in India" focuses on the impact of literacy and education on empowerment of women as well as the suggestion to improve the changes that need to be considered for women empowerment and economic development.

Suresh, P. & Sivakumar, T. (2017) published their article entitled "Women Empowerment in India- A Changing Scenario." They observed that empowerment of women is essentially the process of upliftment of economic,

Social and political status of women, the traditionally underprivileged ones in the society. It is the process of guarding them against all forms of violence.

There are many studies have done related to Women empowerment but there is no study found adolescence empowerment in reference their Stream, locality and Age. So it is an urgent need to conduct a study to measure the empowerment of adolescent girls higher secondary level. The scale that used for the study, there are 49 statements the scale is divided in 7 sections and each section has 7 statements which are as follows-

1. Power and Entitlements
2. Autonomy and Self-Reliance
3. Decision Making
4. Participation
5. Capacity Building
6. Social, Political and Legal Awareness
7. Exposure to Information Media

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A Study of Empowerment of Adolescent Girls in Higher Secondary Schools of Bareilly District

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To find out empowerment of rural and urban higher secondary girls.
- 2) To find out whether religion is related to empowerment of girls
- 3) To check the empowerment on basis of age group of adolescent girls.
- 4) To explore empowerment of girls on the basis of their academic stream.

IV. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- 1) There is no significant difference in empowerment of rural and urban higher secondary girls.
- 2) There is no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to their religion.
- 3) There is no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to age group.
- 4) There is no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to academic stream

V. RESEARCH DESIGN

To achieve of the objectives of the study the descriptive survey method was used. In the present study the population consists adolescent girls of higher secondary school of Bareilly district through random sampling technique. At the final stage 145 students were selected as sample. Adolescent girl's empowerment scale (AGES-SS) developed and standardizing by Dr. Devendra Singh Sisodia and Dr. Alpana Singh was used to collect the data. For data analysis and testing the hypothesis mean S.D, t-test above and percentage were used as statistical techniques.

VI. INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table No. 1: Comparison of scores of empowerment of rural and urban higher secondary girls

Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	't' value
Rural	39	195.43	27.53	143	.83
Urban	106	191.36	25.51		

It is revealed from table-1 that 't' value of rural and urban higher secondary students is 0.83 which is non significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Thus, hypothesis -1 stating " There is no significant difference in empowerment of rural and urban higher secondary girls " is accepted. Finding signifies that level of empowerment among rural and urban girls is same in Bareilly district.

Table No.2: Comparison of scores of empowerment of Hindu & Muslim higher secondary girls

Groups	N	Mean	S.D	Df	't' value
Hindu	85	193.92	22.92	143	.79
Muslim	60	190.4	30.37		

It is revealed from table – 2 that ‘t’ value of Hindu and Muslim higher secondary students is 0.79 which is non significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Thus, hypothesis -2 “There is no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to their religion” is accepted. Finding signifies that level of empowerment among Hindu and Muslim girls is same in Bareilly district.

Table No.3: Comparison of scores of empowerment of Age Group (16,17,18 years) of higher secondary girls

Source of variance	df	Sum of Squares	Means of Squares	F-Ratio
Between Groups	2	72.9877	36.4938	0.55
Within Group	142	98913.7165	696.5755	
Total				

It is revealed from table -3 that ‘F’ value of age group in higher secondary students is 0.55 which is non significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Thus, hypothesis -3 “There is no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to age group” is accepted. Finding signifies that level of empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to age group is same in Bareilly district.

Table No.4: Comparison of scores of empowerment in stream (Art, Commerce and Science) of Higher secondary girls

Source of variance	df	Sum of Squares	Means of Squares	F-Ratio
Between Groups	2	19052.4058	9526.2029	15.8*
Within Group	142	85629.5704	603.0251	
Total				

It is revealed from table - 4 that ‘F’ value of age group stream (Art, Commerce and Science) in higher secondary students is which is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Thus, hypothesis -4 “There is no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to academic stream” is rejected. Finding signifies that level of empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to academic stream is not same in Bareilly district.

VII. CONCLUSION

The findings revealed that there was no significant difference among higher secondary girls level of adolescent girls empowerment in reference of their locality, age and religion. There is a significant difference among higher secondary girls level of adolescent girls empowerment in reference of their stream. The mean score of girls with science stream was high as compared to Arts and Commerce stream. So, it can be concluded that scientific attitude and temperament makes girls more empowered.

VIII. REFERENCES

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